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SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF CRANIODORSAL COXOFEMORAL LUXATION IN THREE DOGS AND THREE CATS USING A NEW ULTRA-HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE IMPLANT

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Purpose of the work

Coxofemoral luxation is a common traumatic lesion in small animals and is most often caused by road traffic trauma (1). The choice of surgical treatment depends on the type of hip luxation, which occurs usually in a craniodorsal direction and more rarely in a caudodorsal or caudoventral direction (2). The surgical management of hip luxation consists in various hip stabilization techniques, including capsulorrhaphy, extra-articular iliofemoral suture (3) secured with anchors (4) and intra-articular replacement of the femoral head ligament with a synthetic ligament secured by toggle pins (5). Intra-articular surgical treatment has the advantage of replacing the injured round ligament by a biocompatible implant that mimics the biomechanical function of the physiological ligament, thus allowing to restore the stability of the coxofemoral joint and preserve its mobility. However, despite that biomechanical studies have reported promising results in dogs (5), intra-articular surgical techniques secured by toggles have provided variable clinical outcomes across studies, with a recurrence rate of hip joint luxation of up to 24.4% (6). Here we report the utilization of an ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) implant set with a cortical button and secured by a femoral interference screw as a concrete solution to replace the round ligament and restore long-term stability of the the coxofemoral joint.

Materials and used methods

Three cats, all males, and three dogs, one female and two males, were presented following a road traffic trauma and were diagnosed with a unilateral craniodorsal hip luxation during clinical orthopedic examination. One cat and two dogs were also diagnosed with concomitant orthopedic lesions (trochanter avulsion and comminuted tibial fracture for the cat, Slater Harris type 3 proximal tibia for the first dog, and radio-carpal luxation for the second dog). A Novalig® implant (Novetech Surgery, Monaco) set with a cortical button and secured by a femoral interference screw was used for the intra-articular replacement of the disrupted round ligament to stabilize the articulation. A first femoral tunnel was drilled from the distal base of the great trochanter to the fovea capitis. A second femoral tunnel was drilled perpendicularly to the first one in a more distal position. A third tunnel was drilled through the acetabulum on the round ligament footprint. The cortical button of the ligament was passed through the acetabular tunnel and securely positioned on the medial aspect of the acetabulum. The ligament was then passed in the first femoral tunnel, and the hip was reduced. Then the implant was passed through the second femoral tunnel, tensioned, and secured by an interference screw. Immediate postoperative radiographs were performed. Phone call follow-ups were available for only one cat and one dog at 3 weeks and 7 months, respectively. A second dog got a clinical examination with radiographs at 6 weeks.

Outcomes

Cats were aged between 16 and 39 months old (mean age 24.6 months \pm 12.5) and weighted between 3.5 and 5.6 kg (mean weight 4.4 kg \pm 1). Dogs were 9 to 44 months old (mean age 23 months \pm 18.5) and weighted between 8 and 18.5 kg (mean weight 14.8 kg \pm 5.9). The mean time from trauma to surgery was 5.8 days \pm 3.6, ranging from 3 to 12 days. The three cats were operated without any per-operative difficulties. Difficulties occurred during surgery for the three dogs and included implant rupture in all cases, associated with the rupture of the interference screw in one case. These difficulties were successfully resolved by implanting a new implant for all dogs, and performing

a capsulorrhaphy for the first dog, inserting the interference screw in the femoral neck for the second dog, and by implanting a new interference screw for the third dog. The cortical buttons of the damaged implants were still in place at the end of the surgery for the three patients as well as the broken interference screw for the second patient. Immediate postoperative radiographs indicated a good positioning of the implant and no postoperative complications occurred. One of the cat owners and one of the dog owners reported a normal mobility with no lameness at 3 weeks and 7 months postoperatively, respectively. A clinical examination with radiographs of a second dog at 6 weeks post-surgery also indicated a normal mobility with no lameness.

Conclusions

Immediate postoperative examinations and radiographs indicated a satisfactory reduction with good stability of the craniodorsal coxofemoral luxation for each patient. The available follow-ups also indicated satisfactory outcomes. Craniodorsal coxofemoral luxation can be successfully treated with an intra-articular stabilization using an UHMWPE implant to replace the damaged round ligament. However, more cases and longer follow-ups must be gathered to further confirm these results. Finally, the ongoing development of a new tap prototype will help improving this intra-articular reconstruction technique by reducing the risk of implant and screw breakage in bone tunnels.

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Disclosure Statement

No

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